

The Word *gid* in Najdi Arabic: An Evidentiality Head

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Abstract

This research paper investigates the word *gid* which is used in Najdi Arabic, a dialect spoken in Najd region in Arabic peninsula. This particle is analyzed syntactically using the recent assumptions of the minimalist program (Chomsky, 1993, 1995, and subsequent work). As for the findings, it turns out that *gid* functions as a head that instantiates its maximal projection above TP and under CP. So, this word is not a property of TP domain nor a CP domain. Due to the fact that this word is only used when a speaker is certain of the propositional content of his/her utterance, we argue that *gid* is an evidential head that scopes over the tense layer. Furthermore, we argue that *gid* has an EPP feature, hence the specifier position of the functional phases headed by it must be filled by some element which is the subject. This accounts for the fact that subject must precede *gid* in declarative sentences. Additionally, *gid* has [PAST] feature which is uninterpretable and hence must be deleted before the derivation is handed over to the LF following the general lines of feature deletion of Chomsky (1995, 2005). We argue that the deletion of [PAST] feature is conducted through an *Agree* operation that is established between *gid* and the verb. This is why *gid* comes exclusively with past tense. Otherwise [PAST] feature on *gid* remains active, leading to the ungrammaticality of the given sentence.

Keywords: Evidentiality, the EPP feature, agree operation, TP, probing

1. Introduction¹

Investigating grammaticality of words and their syntactic functions is for long considered as one of the main destinations of both synchronic and diachronic syntax (Brinton, 1996, Hopper & Traugott, 2003, Trousdale, 2008, Thepkanjana & Ruangmanee, 2015). The importance of such studies lies in the assumption that grammaticalized words and their syntactic functions bring to us reliable clues of how languages are developing and how syntactic functions are carried out and represented in discourse (Hopper & Traugott, 2003, DeLancey, 2004, & Heine, 2006, among many others). Accordingly, grammaticalized words are significant clues of language processing as well as evolution. One such is expressing evidential through grammaticalized items. What this basically means is that when a speaker uses these constructions or grammatical items, he/she is evident that the propositional content of the utterance is right for the best of his/her knowledge. The paper discusses expressing evidentiality in NA morphologically using the active participle and periphrastically through syntactic relations using the grammaticalized word: *gid*.²

This paper is structured as follows: Section 2 gives a brief background about Najdi Arabic. It also sheds light on some syntactic properties of NA, e.g., word order, subject-verb agreement, NA as being a pro-drop language. In section 3, the concept of evidentiality is discussed. In section 4, evidentiality in Arabic is introduced. In section 5, the main descriptive facts related to the syntactic behaviour of the word *gid* are introduced. Section 6 investigates the syntactic behaviour of the particle. Section 7 introduces the semantic function of the evidential particle *gid*. Section 8 concludes the paper.

2. Objectives and Methodology

The aim of this paper is to look into the semantics and syntax of the particle GID in NA. Its aim is to respond to the following research questions:

- What is the semantic function of the particle GID in NA?
- What is the base position of the particle GID in NA? And Where does it reside?

The researchers take a descriptive-analytical approach to their analysis. The data used here is a compilation of genuine Najdi Arabic sentences spoken by 25 native speakers. The un/grammaticality of sentences is judged according to the informants' intuition.

3. Najdi Arabic: A Brief Background

Najdi Arabic is one of the Gulf dialects spoken in the region of Najd which is located in the middle of Saudi Arabia. Najd refers to the area which spreads from Yemen to the south, to the borders Jordan to the north, and from the oasis Al-Ahsa to the east, to the mountains of Hijaz to the west (Al-Sweel, 1981). The location of Najd region is shaded in red in the map below (from Lewis 2013, p. 3)³.

¹ I use the following abbreviations: NA= Najdi Arabic; EPP= Extended Projection Principle; TP= Tense Phrase; VP= Verb Phrase; FP= Focus Phrase; T= Tense; CP= Complementizer Phrase; SG=Singular; PL=Plural; DEF=the definite article (the); M=Masculine; F=Feminine

² While *gid* is sometimes affricated into *ǧzid* in Najdi Arabic, the latter is mostly used as an alternative variant by old people, whereas the former is commonly used among youths.

³ According to Lewis (2013), there are approximately ten million speakers of Najdi Arabic.

Figure 1: Najd Region of Saudi Arabia

2.1 Word order in Najdi Arabic

The word order in NA is flexible. NA can exhibit all possible word orders; SVO, VSO, VOS, OVS, and OSV. Consider the following sentences (1a-e) which show these word orders, respectively.⁴

(1) a. al-wald jaaf al-mbaaraat (SVO)
DEF-boy watch.3SG.M.PAST DEF-match

‘The boy watched the match.’

b. jaaf al-wald al-mbaaraat (VSO)
watch.3SG.M.PAST DEF-boy DEF-match

‘The boy watched the match.’

c. jaaf al-mbaaraat al-wald (VOS)
watch.3SG.M.PAST DEF-match DEF-boy

‘The boy watched the match.’

d. al-mbaaraat jaaf-əh al-wald (OVS)
DEF-match watch.3SG.M.PAST-3SG.F DEF-boy

‘The boy watched the match.’

e. al-mbaaraat al-wald jaaf-əh (OSV)
DEF-match DEF-boy watch.3SG.M.PAST-3SG.F

‘The boy watched the match.’

As we can see from the previous sentences that the word order in NA is free. However, it should be noted that the unmarked (i.e., basic) word order in NA is the SVO, whereas the VSO word order is the marked order (see, e.g., Alshammari, 2018, Alshamari, 2016; Lewis, 2013 for a related discussion). As for the subject-verb agreement, it can be concluded from the examples above (1a-e) that the subject in NA shows full agreement (i.e., person, number and gender) with its subject irrespective of the word order.⁵ Another salient property of NA is that it is a null-copula language. The copula is only overtly expressed in the past tense. See the examples below:

(2) a. Ahmad mdrris
Ahmad teacher

‘Ahmad is a teacher.’

b. Ahmad kaan mdrris
Ahmad BE.3SG.M.PAST teacher

‘Ahmad was a teacher.’

NA is also a pro-drop language. The pronoun/DP subject can be omitted under certain pragmatic circumstances.⁶ Consider the following illustrative examples.

(3) a. (hu) d3aa
he come.3SG.M.PAST

‘He came.’

b. (hii) d3at
she come.3SG.F.PAST

‘She came.’

c. (ahmad) d3aa
Ahmad come.3SG.M.PAST

⁴ All the examples in this paper are from NA, unless otherwise indicated.

⁵ Modern Standard Arabic (MSA, henceforth) shows asymmetries when it comes to subject-verb agreement. While the verb agrees fully with its subject in the SVO word order, it shows a partial agreement (i.e., only in person and gender) with its subject in the VSO word order. See the following examples from Soltan (2007, p. 34).

i a. al-ʔawlaad-u garʔa-u ad-dars-a (SVO+full agreement)
DEF-boys read.3M-PL DEF-lesson-ACC

‘The boys read the lesson.’

b. garʔa al-ʔawlaad-u ad-dars-a (VSO+partial agreement)
read.3SG.M DEF-boys DEF-lesson-ACC

‘The boys read the lesson.’

⁶ For more information about NA as a pro-drop language, see Al-Tamimi (2015).

Al-Dufir	<i>ċāsb-īn</i>	u	lā	‘alē-ham ⁷
Al-Dafir	PART-winners	and	not	by-them

‘And then the news came to him and they brought him good news that the Al-Dafir had won the battle and that there was nothing wrong with them.’

According to Isaksson (2000), the active participle *ċāsb-īn* ‘PART-winners’ in a nominal clause in example (6), giving the news a stative state, expresses reportive evidentiality. Below are examples of active participle that function to encode evidentiality in NA.

(10) aħmad	gaari	ʔal-kitaab
Ahmad	has read	DEF-book

‘Ahmad already read the book (I know).’

(11) aħmad	fari	sijjaarrah
Ahmad	has bought	car

‘Ahmad already bought a car (I know).’

(12) axuuk	kaasir	ad-dirdʒ
borthr.2 nd SM	has broken	DEF-drawer

‘Your brother has broken the drawer (I know).’

In (10) the active participle *gaarij* ‘has read’ indicates that the book was read and the speaker has a second-hand information of evidence on this. Similarly, this applies to sentences (11) and (12). Sometimes, an optional *nunation* [-in] is suffixed to the active participle, but with no change in meaning. Consider the following sentence.

(13) aħmad	gaari(-jin)	ʔal-kitaab
Ahmad	has read	DEF-book

‘Ahmad has read the book (I know).’

As noticed in (13) when the nunation [-in] enters into the active participle, the word sometimes gets resyllabified. Nunation in NA corresponds to *tanwīn* in Classical Arabic, which signifies adding a suffix [-un] ‘indefinite nominative’, [-in] ‘indefinite genitive’, or [-an] ‘indefinite accusative’. However, the function of this suffix has been lost. In NA, it occurs in non-final positions where a noun is followed by a modifying element (Ingham, 1994).⁸ Of note is that the active participle can also have a future reference point when used to signify the future perfect of time/condition clause structures, conveying an intention and/or volition to put the proposed action into practice within the near future (See Ingham, 1994, p. 100-102, for more details).

The active participle functioning to encode evidentiality in NA appears to be similar to evidential discussed by Procházka (2018, 2020) of Arabic dialects spoken in Turkey, particularly in Cilicia and the Harran–Urfa region. Questions on whether this change has spread from Arabic dialects spoken in Turkey to NA and whether such change was originated from language-contact situations with Turkish need further study.

A similar particle to *gid* used in NA is *qad*, which is found in Modern Standard Arabic/Classical Arabic, and functions to encode uncertainty of events that are not yet completed, similar to the English modal ‘may’, if followed by an imperfective verb. With the perfective verb form, however, *qad* expresses certainty and completeness. Wright (1967, p. 286) indicates that “[i]t also serves to mark the position of a past act or event as prior to the present time or to another past act or event, and consequently expresses merely [the English] Perf. or Pluperf.”. On the other hand, Dahl and Talmoudi (1979) argue that *qad* has a pragmatic evidential function (Danks, 2011, p. 161). With *qad* > *gid*, where *q* > *g* is not uncommon in NA, and with similar function, i.e., *gid* expresses a pragmatic evidential function, one may propose that the etymon of *gid* is *qad*.

4. Descriptive facts and preliminary analysis

In this section, the main descriptive facts related to the syntactic behaviour of the word *gid* are introduced in addition to providing preliminary analysis to the emerging observations. The major focus is placed on the position of this word as relative to the tense and the main verb in the respective sentence. Surveying the natural examples where this word is used in NA, it is quite clear that the word *gid* occupies some position which is higher than the main verb. Put it differently, the main verb must follow the word *gid*, otherwise the respective sentence bears ungrammatical. Consider the following sentences.⁹

(14) ʔana	<i>gid</i>	gareit	ʔal-kitaab
I	GID	read.PAST.1SM	DEF-book

‘I have already read this book.’

(15) *ʔana	gareit	<i>gid</i>	ʔal-kitaab
I	read.PAST.1SM	GID	DEF-book

Intended: ‘I have already read the book.’

In (14) the main verb *gareit* ‘read, past’ follows the word *gid*, hence the sentence is grammatical. On the other hand, in (15), the verb precedes the word *gid*, thus the sentence is ungrammatical. This restriction on the position of the main verb relative to *gid* still holds if tense is overtly filled by a tense filler like *kaan* ‘was’. Consider the following sentences.

(16) ʔana	<i>gid</i>	kint	gareit	ʔal-kitaab
I	GID	was.1S	read.1SM	DEF-book

‘I have already read this book.’

(17) *ʔana	gareit	<i>gid</i>	kint	ʔal-kitaab
I	read.1SM	GID	was.1S	DEF-book

⁷ I have maintained as much as possible the transcription and gloss of the original text.

⁸ See Qafisheh (1997) on *nunation* of active participle in Gulf Arabic dialects for more details.

⁹ We gloss *gid* as GID until the point is clear that it is an evidential head.

Intended: 'I have already read the book.'

As a result, one condition for the position of the word *gid* relative to the verb and tense is possible. This condition is as follows:

(18) The word *gid* precedes the verb and the tense used in the respective sentence.

This condition is important to pin down where the word *gid* enters the derivation, as we will explain below in detail. The impossibility of the verb and tense to cross the word *gid* is a reliable sign that the latter is a head rather than an XP. If the word *gid* is a phrase, its presence to the left of the verb would not block the verb head movement to an upper head position, following the general lines of the Relativized Minimality (Rizzi, 1990, 2013). The fact that *gid* blocks the verb movement strongly implies that the two elements belong to the same phrasal status, namely heads. If the word *gid* is not a head, its presence to the left of verb and to the left of the tense filler does not also block the movement of the latter to a higher position above the functional phrase housing the word *gid* (as in 19B below). On the other hand, if the word *gid* is a head, its presence to the left of main verb and to the left of tense filler blocks the movement of the latter to a higher position that is situated above the functional phrase housing the word *gid*. That is because, for instance, tense filler as a head must first occupy the head position of the functional phrase housing the word *gid*, and then moves further to a higher position. The word *gid* functioning as a head blocks this potential movement given that the functional phrase housing the word *gid* is filled by *gid* per se (as in 19A below). Consider the following schematic presentations.

(19)

The restriction that tenses filler and the main verb must appear to the right of *gid* without any possibility for crossing over *gid* is strong evidence for the headedness of *gid* (cf. Matushansky, 2006, among others).

What is worth investigating at this point is the obvious observation that *gid* subcategorizes for a verbal complement with past tense interpretation. In other words, the complement of the word *gid* must be a verb in past tense. If a verb appearing to the right of *gid* is in its present tense, the sentence becomes ungrammatical. Consider the following sentence.

(20) *ʔana *gid* agra ʔal-kitaab
 I GID read.PRES.1SM DEF-book

Intended: 'I am reading the book.'

The ungrammaticality of the sentence in (20) remains even if the verb is in future tense, i.e., preceded by the future auxiliary *rah* 'will'.

(21) *ʔana *gid* rah ʔagra ʔal-kitaab
 IGID will read.PRES.1SM DEF-book

Intended: 'I will read the book.'

Accordingly, it can be concluded that the word *gid* is only licensed when it is followed by a past tense verb. The fact that *gid* is not followed by an imperfective verb indicates that verb following *gid* is not in its thematic position, heading the VP. Following Benmamoun (2000) and Aoun, Benmamoun and Choueiri (2009), we argue that the past tense of the verb is derived through verb movement to Tense. Consider the following schematic representation of how the past tense of the verb is derived.

(22)

Along the line of this analysis, the word *gid* is followed by TP rather than vP/VP. This claim can be corroborated when sentences with overt tense are taken into account. As we hinted to above, *gid* can be followed by the tense filler, *kaan* 'was' and the sentence holds grammatical. Consider the sentences in (23) and (24).

(23) ʔana *gid* kint gareit ʔal-kitaab
 I GID was.1S read.1SM DEF-book

'I have already read this book.'

(24) *ʔana kint *gid* gareit ʔal-kitaab
 I was.1S GID read.1SM DEF-book

'Intended: I have already read this book.'

This being the case, it can be safely argued now that the maximal projection headed by *gid* is situated above TP; otherwise, the fact that *gid* is followed by a past tense is hard to account for within the recent generative theorizing that bans downward movement (Chomsky, 1993, 1995, 2005). So, the direct and simple proposal is that the functional layer headed by *gid* is situated directly above TP in the respective

clause. This proposal accounts for the sub-categorizational properties of *gid* in that the complement follows the head not the other way round.

4.1 Syntactic analysis of *gid*: *gid* as a head phrase

Let us investigate the first question (why does the subject appear to the left of *gid* although it is expected to be in the Spec position of TP?). Drawing on our account that the functional phrase headed by *gid* c-commands TP, it is expected that the subject appears to the right of *gid*, which is contrary to fact. Consider the following examples.

- (25) *ʔana* *gid* *gareit* *ʔal-kitaab*
 I AUX read.PAST.1SM DEF-book

‘I have already read the book.’

- (26) **gid* *ʔana* *gareit* *ʔal-kitaab*
 AUX I read.PAST.1SM DEF-book

Intended: ‘I have already read the book.’

Subject must be to the left of *gid*. For this, we argue that *gid* as a head has an EPP feature within its featural make-up. It is the EPP feature on *gid* that forces the subject to vacate Spec, TP in declarative sentences to move to Spec, FP which is headed by *gid*. Along these lines, it can be postulated that the subject moves out of its thematic position to Spec, TP satisfying the EPP feature on T. Then, it moves to Spec, FP headed by *gid*, as schematized in the following structure (the subject movement is boldfaced).

In this way, the obligatory position of the subject in declarative sentences to the left of *gid* is explained. One might ask here a question of how the EPP feature of *gid* is satisfied in cases where there is no overt subject, given the null-subject status of the NA. Consider the following sentences.

- (28) *gid* *gareit* *ʔal-kitaab*
 GID read.PAST.1SM DEF-book

‘I have already read the book.’

- (29) *gid* *gara* *ʔal-kitaab*
 GID read.PAST.3SM DEF-book

‘He has already read the book.’

- (30) *gid* *garat* *ʔal-kitaab*
 GID read.PAST.3Sf DEF-book

‘She has already read the book.’

In sentences in (28) through (30), there is no overt subject to the left of *gid*, but all sentences remain grammatical though. For such cases, we follow the widely-held assumption for Arabic sentence that in sentences with no overt subject, the subject position is filled by null *pro* whose identity is detected through the inflections appearing on the verb (see, for example Fassi Fehri, 1993, Al-Aqarbeh, 2011; Versteegh, 2014 in this regard). It is clear from the examples in (28) through (30) that the verb has different inflectional forms, depending on the identity of the hidden subject. In such cases, we argue that Spec, FP headed by *gid* is occupied by *pro* which is base-generated in Spec, VP in cases of transitive sentences or in Spec, VP in cases on intransitive sentences. Then this *pro*, analogous to cases with overt subject, moves to Spec, TP, then to Spec FP headed by *gid*.¹⁰ As such, the EPP feature on *gid* is satisfied by *pro*. What is important to note at this point is that the null *pro* can move from its thematic position to higher positions. The null *pro* thus can meet the EPP features on T and *gid* alike, and hence there is no need to deploy a different strategy to meet the EPP features on T or *gid*.

As for the second question (why must the verb following *gid* be in past tense?), we argue that the word *gid* as a head has an uninterpretable PAST feature in its featural make-up. Given Chomsky’s assumptions (1995) on that uninterpretable feature must be deleted before handing the derivation over to the LF components, we argue that the word *gid* enters syntactic operation with tense to value this feature. Before elaborating on this claim, consider the Principle of Full interpretation (FI):

- (31) The principle FI is assumed as a matter of course in phonology; if a symbol in a representation has no sensorimotor interpretation, the representation does not qualify as a PF representation. This is what we called the “interface condition”. The same condition applied to LF also entails that every element of the representation have [*sic*] a (language independent) interpretation (Chomsky, 1995, p. 27).

This principle was reformulated as the interpretability condition which states the following:

¹⁰ We still argue following the mainstream assumptions held for the Arabic sentence (cf. Aoun *et al* 2010, Fassi Fehri 2012) that Spec, TP must be projected due to the EPP feature on T. Whether this assumption is valid or not lies beyond the scope of this paper.

(32)

The Interpretability Condition: LIs [lexical items] have no features other than those interpretable at the interface, the properties of sound and meaning. (Chomsky, 2000, p. 113)

The condition in (29) indicates that the lexical items do not have any uninterpretable features at the interface levels; if there are some features, they have to be deleted. Only the features that have semantic and phonological contents are permitted to reach the interface levels. The question now is how the uninterpretable PAST feature on the word *gid* is deleted. We here make recourse to the Agree operation to account for the deletion of this feature. Chomsky (2001) argued for certain conditions on the Agree relation between the searching probe and the matching goal (2001, p. 122). These conditions are as follows:

(33)

The probe α agrees with the goal β provided that:

- a- α has uninterpretable φ -features.
- b- β has matching (un)interpretable φ features.
- c- β is active by virtue of having an unvalued Case feature.
- d- α c-commands β .
- e- There is no potential goal γ intervening between α and β .

Given that the word *gid* has PAST feature which is uninterpretable, the claim is that the word *gid* is an active probe. It starts looking for its domain for an active goal that has a matching PAST feature which must be interpretable. Let us first focus on the cases where the verb is in the past tense as in (25) which is repeated below as (34) for convenience.

(34) ?ana *gid* gareit ?al-kitaab
I GID read.PAST.1SM DEF-book

'I have already read the book.'

We argue that the word *gid* finds the verb adjoining the tense (cf. Benmamoun, 2000; Aoun et al, 2010). The verb is endowed with an interpretable matching PAST feature. Consequently, an Agree relation is established between the word *gid* and the verb, while the latter is in the past tense. This relation results in deleting the uninterpretable matching PAST feature on the word *gid*.

On the other hand, in cases where the verb is in the present tense or the imperfective form (as in the sentences in (20) and (21) above repeated below as (35)), there is no *Agree* relation established between *gid* and the verb given that the latter does not have a matching interpretable [PAST] feature. This leads to the ungrammaticality of the respective sentence.

(35) *?ana *gid* agra ?al-kitaab
IGID read.PRES.1SM DEF-book

Intended: 'I am reading the book.'

(36) *?ana *gid* raħ ?agra ?al-kitaab
IGID will read.PRES.1SM DEF-book

Intended: 'I will read the book.'

At this point, one might ask a question: why the word *gid* does not inflect for agreement. Consider the following sentences.

(37) *gid-i gareit ?al-kitaab
GID-1S read.PAST.1SM DEF-book

Intended: 'I have already read the book.'

(38) *gid-uh gara ?al-kitaab
GID-3SM read.PAST.3SM DEF-book

Intended: 'He has already read the book.'

(39) *gid-ha garat ?al-kitaab
GID-3SF read.PAST.3Sf DEF-book

Intended: 'She has already read the book.'

For this, we claim that the word *gid* does not have φ -features in its featural bundle, hence the lack of any overt agreement between *gid* and any other element including subject.

4.2 Semantic function of *gid*: *gid* as an evidential particle

The last issue meriting consideration is related to the semantic function of *gid*. We claim that *gid* is an evidential particle in the sense that it denotes higher degrees of evidentiality. It is only used when a speaker is certain on the content of his/her utterance. Evidence for this contention can be adduced from the fact that the word *gid* cannot co-occur with any adverb that expresses probability or lesser degrees of evidentiality. Consider the following sentences.

(40) *gid ?ihtimaal gara ?al-kitaab
EVD probability read.PAST.3SM DEF-book

Intended: 'It is probable that he has already read the book.'

(41) *gid jimkin garat ?al-kitaab
EVD possible read.PAST.3Sf DEF-book

Intended: 'It is possible that she has already read the book.'

Accordingly, it can be postulated that *gid* is a head that projects an evidentiality projection between CP and TP.

5. Results and Discussion

This work explores the word *gid* in NA utilizing the recent assumptions of the minimalist program (Chomsky, 1993, 1995, 2000, 2001, and 2005). *gid* is an evidential head that instantiates its own projection situated between CP and TP. In order to account for the fact that the subject must precede this word in declarative sentences, we argue that *gid* has an EPP feature, hence the specifier position of the evidentiality Phrase headed by *gid* is filled by a subject. In order to account for why *gid* subcategorizes for past verbs, we argue that *gid* has [PAST] feature which is uninterpretable and hence must be deleted before the derivation is handed over to the LF. We postulate that the deletion of [PAST] feature is conducted through an agree operation that is established between *gid* and the verb. On the other hand, *gid* does not have φ -features in its featural bundle, hence the lack of any overt agreement between *gid* and any other element including subject. We also discuss the semantic function of *gid* and claim that this word is an evidentiality particle in the sense that it denotes higher degrees of evidentiality.

Bio-Note

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